

THE IDEOLOGY OF PURITAN LITERATURE

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Abstract: The article examines the essence of Puritans' ideology. It reveals a theme of personal salvation, divine providence and the meaning of the phrase 'original sin' in American Puritan literature.

Keywords: Puritan(s), God, elected, original sin.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается сущность идеологии пуритан. В нем раскрывается тема личного спасения, божественного промысла и значение фразы «первородный грех» в американской пуританской литературе.

Ключевые слова: Пуритане, Бог, избранный, первородный грех.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada puritanlar mafkurasining mohiyati ko'rib chiqiladi. U shaxsiy najot mavzusini, ilohiy inoyatni va Amerika puritan adabiyotidagi "asl gunoh" iborasining ma'nosini ochib beradi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Puritanlar, Xudo, tanlangan, asl gunoh.

«The Puritans, who came to Massachusetts Bay after the Pilgrims came to Plymouth, came to set up a theocracy, a "city on the hill" that would show the rest of Europe, especially England with its religion that they regarded as corrupted, just what a religious community could be. They were quite vibrant, and the ministers were the community leaders».¹

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<https://archive.vcu.edu/english/engweb/puritantheology.htm#:~:text=Their%20doctrines%20stressed%20original%20sin,chosen%20to%20save%20a%20few>

‘Original sin’... the meaning of this phrase is related to first humans, Adam and Eve. They disobeyed God’s warning about Forbidden fruit and were expelled from the Gardens of Eden (from Heaven). According to the ideology of Puritans, all people who are born inherit Adam’s sin. Therefore, even a baby is considered a sinner. In this case, we can conclude that all people are sinners and they all are residents of Hell. Not exactly. There is another interesting term – ‘Elect’.

«American Puritans linked material wealth with God’s favour. They believed that hard work was the way to please God. Created more wealth through one’s work and thrift could guarantee the God’s elect».²

«Jesus died for the chosen Elect only, those predestined for heaven, not for everyone. God's grace, or merciful love, is freely given (to the Elect) but it cannot be earned or resisted. A person cannot "work" his or her way into heaven. However, if truly saved, he or she will want to live as a saint. The Elect have full power to interpret God's will and live uprightly».³ So, only a few elected people by God can be rewarded with Heavens for hard work, by doing good deeds and avoiding evil. Puritans did not have the opportunity to know – who was elect, therefore they always tended to be good, and kind and do only good and do not forget about God’s power and mercy. That is called personal salvation.

At the heart of Puritan theology is the doctrine of the sovereignty of God from which all follows and their doctrine of original sin is related, as everything else is, to that. As all Puritans believed God’s sovereign will predestined the elect to salvation, so Man’s fall into sin in Adam, the original sin by which he is condemned, was also ordained by the permissive will of God.⁴

Critically Perkins writes: For we must not think that man’s fall was either by chance, or God not knowing it, or barely winking at it, or by his bare permission, or against his will: but rather miraculously, not without the will of God, and yet without all approbation of it.⁵

² <https://memoirandremains.com/2012/08/13/puritans-and-wealth-as-a-sign-of-election/>

³ <https://archive.vcu.edu/english/engweb/puritantheology.htm#:~:text=Their%20doctrines%20stressed%20original%20sin.chosen%20to%20save%20a%20few>

⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/city-mission>

⁵ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/city-mission>

Therefore, divine providence means that God predestines everything and even Adam’s sin was the will of God.

Conclusion

Although Puritans consider all human beings as sinners they try to get forgiveness from God, by not knowing if they will be in Hell or Heaven.

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